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PHILOSOPHICAL COMPREHENSION OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND INFORMATION INFLUENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MODERN WORLD

The concepts of “information influence” and “psychological influence” in the light of the history of philosophy allow us to record that their formation was greatly influenced by the socio-cultural transformations that influenced the formation of a new philosophical image of the world, gradually preparing the consideration of such influences as information influence and psychological influence. The supremacy of information technology has created a new reality with new rules. Information warfare between countries and an “information” economy is based on a number of views. Both information and psychological influences play a key role in the above

mentioned. Each information influence implies a psychological influence and vice versa: the psychological influence, in turn, becomes the basis for an information influence.

In this research, the authors have attempted to make a “3D” observation of the issue. First, the authors highlighted the philosophical foundations of information and psychological influences. Second, they showed the mechanisms that cause information and psychological influences. Third, the issue of information security was brought forward, and the issue of dealing with various means of manipulation was raised. The authors considered the information influence from the point of view of its turning into psychological influence, considering the issue in a new light.

Keywords: *psychological influence, information influence, information technologies, psychological manipulation*

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Introduction. In the modern world, information technologies have a significant place and role in the life of an individual. Their influence is huge in almost every sphere of life, as a result of which the issue of providing information, the issue of the specification of the latter, and objectivity have gained crucial importance in all scientific disciplines. It is needless to say, that the influence of information technology has been well studied. In the current geopolitically unstable conditions, however, when the purpose of providing information is mostly of psychological influence, there is a need to redefine concepts and study information and psychological influences in parallel, especially from a philosophical point of view.

The purpose of this research is to highlight the technologies of psychological and information influences in the modern world from a philosophical point of view. To achieve that goal, the following issues were put forward:

1. bring up the philosophical foundations of the origin of the information society;
2. consider the philosophical content of the concepts of “psychological influence” and “information influence”;
3. analyze the influence of information technologies on the individual and the applied manipulative techniques;
4. raise information security mechanisms.

The Peculiarity of Using the terms “psychological influence” and “information influence” in philosophy: Literature review

In the modern world, information technologies have created such a socio-cultural reality that is based heavily on the human-machine interaction and intercommunion. If before man-man, man-society, and man-nature “dialogue” there was an important indicator of preserving the vitality of the individual, then at the end of the XX century and already at the beginning of the XXI century, the environment and subjects of the dialogue have changed, creating a technocentric reality. The latter makes the social reality highly unitary, based on virtual reality, where it is difficult to differentiate between the real, the apparent, the imaginary, and the hyperreal. And, hence, the question arises: what is the breakthrough period, after which a completely new picture of the world was created and, accordingly, the philosophical problems were changed, or when and why did information influence (Wanless & Pamment, 2019) transform into psychological influence?

In philosophy, the answer to the above mentioned question can be sought starting with the philosophy of life, when Nietzsche (1974) took the position of nihilism, and Schopenhauer (1966) considered unwillingness to be an acceptable manifestation of will: in philosophy, the second anthropological turn likely took place, which served as a basis for the creation of a new reality. At the beginning of the XX century, Heidegger (2010), Sartre (2018), Camus (1956), and others, making the third anthropological turn in their philosophical works, put forward the questions of being and time, being and

nothingness, and freedom and absurdity, reflecting the psychological characteristic of the person of the given period. Thus, in the XX century, the individual was dealing with two World Wars, fear and anxiety, undefined freedom, and other existential problems, the solution of which could be found in the new, technocentric reality. A reality in which there was no self-seeking or self-limiting responsibility. Interestingly, the most important tool of the technocentric society has become the achievement of psychological influence through informational influence.

Extending the above-mentioned context, let's distinguish a new human figure, Homo Ludens. Starting from Homo erectus (man walking straight) to Homo Ludens (a playing man), as a result of creating the image of man and distinguishing his/her features, yet in the middle of the XX century, Huizinga (1950) viewed the playing man as a culture-creating phenomenon. And, indeed, since the middle of the XX century, the game in its many manifestations has become the most important element of human activity. It is also considered in psychoanalysis, becoming an important foundation of the new reality (Berne, 1964). Observing Huizinga's point of view of the "playing man" as a figure of a human of technocentric time, let's analyze some concepts of perception of reality in postmodern philosophy and, on this basis, reflect on the peculiarities of using the terms "psychological influence" and "information intervention" at the same time.

Does a person feel the reality in which he/she lives? In answer to this postmodernist question, the postmodernist philosopher Jean Baudrillard (1983) would confidently say "no" because this reality is hyperrealistic. A hyperreality is based on simulation. The latter brings about a hyperreality without any real basis. Therefore, it becomes difficult to distinguish between what is hyperreal and what is real. Based on Baudrillard's concept, one can put forward the hypothesis that in the period of non-distinction of hyperreality and reality, "information influence" plays an essential role as a great tool of psychological influence. How? In our information age, information creates reality, regardless of whether it is objective or subjective. Therefore, by targeting a certain goal, the relevant information is also introduced, which, after circulating, turns into a psychological latent effect. A vivid example of this is the news of both victory and advancement during the days of the war, which turns into a psychological effect. Thoroughly studying the media of the warring parties and the announcements of the leaders of the countries, we will obviously come across opposite information that both sides present as true. So what is true and what is false? This equation has no solution because the dead end of hyperreality is created based on reality.

Let's look back to our emphasis on the transformation from information influence to psychological influence, and discuss another important concept - security. According to some modern philosophers, security is both positive information and negative information, as it informs and protects an individual or a group, but at the same time weakens, and preserves the individual's life at all costs, but, on the other hand, eliminates it with its existence and autonomy (Burdie & Baudrillard, 2018, p. 320). When continuing to discuss the terms "information influence" and "psychological influence" in the context of reality, let's also refer to Zizek's (2002) idea that sometimes a person even tries to find a fulcrum in reality through self-harm, in contrast to the fear that he/she, perhaps, does not exist. In the information society, a person is self-withdrawing to such an extent that even in solitude he/she is deprived of the courage to face himself/herself and it is the body that should remind him/her that he/she exists. It is here that the death of the subject is announced: the subject is divided within itself, or is divided by others. That process makes him an object (Fuko, 2006, p. 161): this is the fourth anthropological turn.

Observing the peculiarities of the terms "information influence" and "psychological influence" especially in postmodern philosophy, an attempt was made

not to make a terminological analysis, but to show the causality, and discuss the reasons for the origination of the mentioned terms, their transformations and their influence.

Research Methodology. The following general methods were used in the research: system, comparative, synthesis, and analysis. The system method allowed authors to consider the essence of modern mechanisms of influence as a whole. Thanks to the system method, the peculiarities of the discussion of the issue in the history of philosophy and other related sciences were highlighted. A number of features of informational and psychological impact were put forward, which were coordinated according to the logic of the discussion of the issue, thanks to which the order and structure of the discussion of the issues, put forward in the research, were formed.

The comparative and analysis methods revealed the features of the mechanisms of information and psychological impact in terms of information security. The comparative method allowed the authors to draw parallels between different philosophical perceptions of the issue, highlight the differences and similarities of these perceptions, emphasize their role from the point of view of the philosophical study of informational and psychological influences.

The use of the synthesis method made it possible to present relevant conclusions and recommendations as a result of the analysis. Thanks to the synthesis method, by combining the already acquired data, the authors got a complete picture of the discussion of the issue, combined the most effective informational and psychological methods in the light of the problems of the modern world, emphasized their application in the modern society.

The analysis method was also used by the authors in order to show the modern importance of psychological and informational influences. The authors analyzed the modern mechanisms of dealing with them, how to cope with informational and psychological influences in the conditions of the modern, technocentric world.

The synthesis and analysis methods used in the work made it possible to identify the philosophical roots of psychological and information influence, solving the problem of defining these concepts in a philosophical sense, and the system and comparative methods allowed to coordinate and combine the obtained data, as a result of which the study of the problem got a final shape.

The psychological influence of the information environment on a modern man

Within the conditions of modern civilization, reality doubles as “real reality” and “imposed reality”, which is nothing more than media-depicted reality. Everything we know about our society and even the world, we learn through mass media. On the other hand, we have already heard so much about mass media that we simply cannot trust that source (Luhmann, 2000, p. 9).

We are dealing not so much with the phenomenon of distortion of reality, but with the means of constructing our own reality by the mass media. Strengthening public critical reflection is hindered by market and government interests, which initially seek to ensure the manageability of the public sphere. The latter, under the influence of mass media, becomes a politically passive role player over time. The mass media, being under the influence of economic and political structures, lead the political activism of the public to silent consumption of media output (Habermas, 1991).

In the modern world, the Western culture has introduced the following belief into people’s minds, that mass media are a link between the public and a certain objective reality. However, it should be taken into account that journalists and analysts, providing information about objective reality to the public, consider their main task to please the audience. In the information market, as in any market, the primary concern is the sales of the product (in this case, information).

On the basis of informational selection the search for lurid, exclusive, and original material is under way. The media field, turning events into a media representation,

makes the imaginary real by imposing the reality it creates. By applying technologies that affect the mind and psychology of a person, they create a unique virtual reality, which is characterized by the blurring of the boundaries between the real and unreal worlds, and the absence of understanding of the causality. In this case, a person is not capable of making responsible decisions in accordance with the created situation. Critical and analytical judgments give way to imitation, where inevitably the individual loses the objective standards of truth. The latter is replaced by the understandings and opinions circulating in the media space, by which the individual begins to be guided and acts accordingly.

In modern reality, the media is a substantial social institution that plays a major role in shaping the human mind, forcing people to believe what is presented. However, as everyone imitates others, tries to get ahead of them, and delivers information earlier or differently than others do, the result is that everyone does the same thing with minor differences, which leads to uniformity. Although media outlets are pursuing different gains and interests, with different audiences, the distinctions are not significant either in terms of style or in terms of content. In addition, competition often leads to using technology to attract audiences in easy ways.

The mass media have the power to create and enforce certain social perceptions. Realizing the function of “disguised coercion”, they change the vector of human behavior, goals, desires, intentions, relationships, and attitudes through unique technologies of information and psychological influence. In addition, they mostly affect the emotional field of the public, ignoring the conscious side, as they mainly deal with topics that do not require serious mental effort and special knowledge. In the texts presented as analysis, several labels are used, which, besides forming a negative emotional atmosphere, contribute to the polarization of the society whose formation is also facilitated by the media’s partial presentation of social reality, when the media only present what is pleasing to their audience and do not try to address opposing views.

In modern conditions, during political struggle, economic competition, and interstate and military conflicts, the factors of information and psychological influence are of great importance both on the interstate and domestic levels.

Manipulation as a form of covert coercion of psychological influence

The issue of media influence on the human mind and behavior is related to the issue of communication technologies. According to the approach adopted in the academic literature (Dzialoshinskii, 2006), these technologies can be classified into three groups:

1. white technologies: information, persuasion, dialogue;
2. gray technologies: imitation, infection, inspiration;
3. black technologies: manipulation, psychological coercion, information violence.

Informational and psychological influence is a means of influencing people (individuals and groups), the purpose of which is to change the ideological and psychological structures of their consciousness and subconscious, transform their emotional state, stimulate certain types of behavior using informational means and various means of overt and covert psychological coercion. Psychological manipulation is often used in the form of covert coercion technologies.

Forms of covert coercion include psychological manipulation. Psychological manipulation is a means of psychological influence, the purpose of which is to change the direction of mental and other activities of other people which is implemented inconspicuously for them. Manipulating people’s minds is a method of management by imposing favorable ideas, positions, motives, and behavior stereotypes through human influence on the subject.

This technology is becoming popular since it is mostly used in politics, advertising, public relations, and journalism. Currently, manipulation is perceived as a

system of means of ideological and socio-psychological influence, whose purpose is to change people's way of thinking and behavior against their interests. The main features of manipulation are (Dzialoshinskii, 2006):

- the process of manipulation is disproportionate: there is an influencing party (subject) and an influenced party (object);
- manipulation is a type of spiritual or psychological influence (rather than physical violence or the threat of violence). The manipulator's target is the person's mental structure;
- manipulation is a covert influence, a fact which should not be noticed by the object of manipulation.

Three levels of manipulation are distinguished:

- the 1st level strengthens the necessary ideas, attitudes, motives, values, and norms existing in people's minds;
- the 2nd level is related to private, small changes in views about this or that event, process and facts which also affect the emotional and practical attitude towards a specific phenomenon;
- the 3rd level which leads to radical change of vital positions through communicating new, surprising, unusual, dramatic, and important information (data) to the object.

According to researchers, the success of manipulation is guaranteed when the manipulated person believes that everything that happens is natural and inevitable (Shiller, 1980, pp. 27-28). That is why mass media have gained great relevance and growing importance: they become important tools for implementing political processes, managing the public minds, and shaping public opinion. In the modern world, mass media control our entire culture, and by passing it through its filters, distinguish individual elements from the general cultural phenomena and give them a special weight, increasing the value of one idea, and devaluing another, thus polarizing the entire field of culture. What has not appeared in the mass communication channels has almost no influence on the development of the society in our time (Atoyan et al., 2015, p. 56). Therefore, nowadays, mass media have turned from simple means of information search, processing, and transmission into means of controlling and transforming the inner world of a person, more and more harshly manipulating the minds of the masses through spreading behavioral stereotypes (Abdigalieva & Toktarov, 2012).

Practically it has been established that the more informed people are, the more difficult it is to manipulate them, so the objects of psychological influence should be provided with a substitute for information, chopped and diluted which corresponds to the goals of psychological influence. At first, they try to impose such stereotypes on people that are capable of producing the necessary reactions, actions, and behavior. Moreover, specially oriented (or specially selected) are those who believe in myths and rumors against their will. Then some so-called tricks are used that allow the increase of the effectiveness of the influence:

- provision of "necessary" information at the given moment, often crudely prepared information;
- deliberate concealment of true and truthful information;
- providing information overload which makes it difficult for the object of influence to find out the true nature of things.

When the lie is discovered, the severity of the situation assumably decreases over time, and a lot of things are perceived as natural, necessary, or in extreme cases, forced.

Manipulation of information includes a number of methods:

1. *Information overload*. A huge amount of information is provided, the main part of which is abstract judgements, unimportant details, various trivial things, and other "informational garbage". As a result, the object cannot comprehend the true nature of the problem.

2. *Information quantity.* Only part of the information is provided and the rest is diligently concealed. It leads to the fact that reality is distorted to one extent or becomes totally obscure.
3. *A big lie.* The essence of this trick is that the more disrespectful and untrue a lie is, the sooner it will be believed: the main thing is to provide it as seriously as possible.
4. *Mixing real facts with the most possible assumptions, hypotheses, and rumors.* As a result, it becomes impossible to differentiate the truth from the fiction.
5. *Time delay.* This trick leads to delaying the provision of really important information under various pretexts until it is too late to change anything.
6. *Strike back.* The essence of this trick is that a fabricated (naturally, favorable to the fabricator) version of this or that event is spread by a third party through media neutral to the opposing parties. The press of the competing side (opposing) usually repeats this version because it is considered more “objective” than the opinions of the direct participants in the conflict.
7. *A lie told on time.* Completely false, but highly expected (“fresh”) information is provided. The more the content of the provision corresponds to the mood of the object, the more fruitful is its result. Then the lie is revealed, but in the meantime, the severity of the situation decreases or a certain process becomes irreversible.

Mass media change the meaning of words and concepts to manipulate minds. Moreover, the context is changed, and a completely different meaning is created from the same words. Separate “pieces” of information may not appear to be fake, but the whole package made by a reporter or an editor may have nothing in common with reality.

The basic tricks of semantic manipulation are (Ohanyan, 2022):

- simplification and stereotyping;
- assertion and repetition;
- fragmentation;
- urgency;
- scoop.

Simplification and stereotyping. Mass media has played one of the most vital roles in the process of turning society into a crowd. A crowd man is a product of mosaic culture, mostly created by the mass media. Unlike high culture, mass media is meant for the masses. Therefore, strict restrictions on the complexity and uniqueness of information have been established in the mass media. The psychological justification for this rule is that people subconsciously seek simplistic explanations for complex problems (Kara-Murza, 2015, p. 289).

In the 20ies of the XX century, the concept of simplification was proposed by the W. Lippmann who considered that the process of perception is just a mechanical adaptation of an unknown phenomenon to a general fixed formula, i.e. a stereotype (Dzialoshinskii, 2006). For this reason, mass media should standardize the phenomenon that has become the object of information. Moreover, the editor must rely on stereotypes and trivial opinions and ruthlessly ignore nuances. A person should perceive information effortlessly and mutely, without internal struggle and critical analysis. The simplification operation is followed by conversion into symbols, i.e. the search for the most appropriate words to represent the primitive models. Thus, the processing of ready-made information turns into mere project work.

Assertion and repetition. Simplification enables one to express the main idea concisely and impressively and as the form of a statement so that the audience should be inspired. Relying on the thinking of a crowd person formed in the mosaic culture, the mass media has simultaneously become an important factor in strengthening that thinking. They have trained people to think in stereotypes and have gradually reduced

the intellectual level of information. This was facilitated by the main method of strengthening the necessary stereotypes in mind—repetition. In this regard, the French psychologist and sociologist Le Bon (1995) stated that repetition is ultimately embedded in the depths of the subconscious, where the motivations for our actions are formed. When you abuse the power of repetition, stereotypes grow into strong prejudices.

Fragmentation. One of the special and significant aspects of simplification is the breaking down of a whole problem into separate parts so that the listener, reader, or audience cannot put them together and make sense of the problem. It is the fundamental principle of mosaic culture. Fragmentation is carried out by many techniques: in newspapers, articles are divided into parts and placed on different pages, or the text or TV program is interrupted by advertisements.

The mass media “build” the seemingly chaotic flow of information in such a way that both the reader and the audience form an image of a such reality that is advantageous to the owner of the information. Information selection criteria are based on well-developed theories and mathematical calculations. For each piece of information, *the level of complexity and distance from the person* is assessed (according to these calculations, the media distinguish 4-5 layers of the depth of the human psyche, to be influenced by the information). From that data, the information is given *a degree of significance*, based on which the newspaper or news program is compiled.

Urgency. One of the conditions for the successful and justified segmentation of the main problems is the urgency of the information, giving it a sense of urgency. An overwhelming sense of urgency is believed to dramatically increase the media’s manipulative capabilities. As a result of daily and hourly information updates, it loses its steady structure. A person simply does not have time to make sense of or understand information because it is forced out by other, newer information. A sense of urgency creates a sense of particular importance to the subject of information and weakens the ability to differentiate information according to the degree of importance. The rapid succession of information about disasters and attacks by armed forces, wastes and strikes, and heat complicates the process of making assessments and judgments. In that case, the mental process of sorting, which under normal conditions contribute to making sense of the information, is violated (Shiller, 1980, p. 11).

Scoop. The use of scoops allows one to ensure the fragmentation of problems and split information in such a way that a person never receives complete and finished knowledge. This is information about events of great significance and uniqueness when almost the entire attention of the audience is focused on it. With the help of scoops, either important events that the public should not notice are covered up, or the scandal and psychosis are stopped, but in such a way that they are forgotten.

The constant “bombardment” of the mind with scoops affecting emotions, especially “bad news”, performs an important function of maintaining the necessary level of “nervousness”. That nervousness, the constant sense of crisis dramatically increases dispirit and reduces the capacity for critical perception. The violation of ordinary and stable social situations always increases the *situational* dispirit.

In modern conditions, information and communication processes use not just separate tricks, but special manipulative technologies (Dotsenko, 1997, pp. 106-144). The use of manipulative technologies as a means of managing people’s behavior and influencing their individual and mass consciousness is carried out during the conduct of foreign policy, in internal political struggle, in the activities of organizations in a state of economic competition and conflict, and the process of interpersonal interaction among people.

However, no matter how terrifying the myth of media omnipotence and “psycho-programming” of mass consciousness and unlimited possibilities of informational and communicative manipulation may seem, they are still means of communication (Ohanyan & Malkjyan, 2014, p. 138). And a person does not just automatically process

the received information, but throws away the useless, individually sorts the information according to the degree of importance, and determines the order of its perception. In this context, E. Fromm in his foundational work “The Anatomy of Human Destructiveness” (Fromm, 1973) emphasizes that people with clearly defined social and political positions are the least manipulated because manipulative influences are inversely proportional to sociocultural identity, education, and group solidarity. Therefore, manipulation as a process is limited by certain boundaries determined by socio-psychological patterns within which an individual or social group can be influenced. Any person interprets the available information by evaluating it which depends on his/her worldview, ideals, social position, and cultural development. Here, the value system acts as a filter that determines the psychological defense system, the main mechanisms of which are denial, repression, projection, identification, rationalization, and withdrawal.

“Information Security” and “Psychological Protection”: philosophical and psychological mechanisms

In the XXI century, when information technologies have a key place and role in the life of an individual and the society, the issue of information security is of primary importance. The Internet, social platforms, and various social networks (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, TikTok, VKontakte, etc.) “collect” excessive information about an individual’s life, activities, and preferences which can be used for manipulation, psychological and other types of influence as serving tools. Taking the above mentioned into account, let’s first try to answer what security is, define the terms “information security” and “psychological protection” and then highlight some mechanisms of information and psychological protection from the point of view of philosophy and psychology.

What is security? Referring to world history, it becomes clear that the term “security” has received different contents in different periods due to the historical, socio-cultural, and why not also the economic situation of the given period. From ancient times till our days, the issue of security has been paramount, largely expressed by physical security, as the religious and political World Wars promoted the issue of physical security first. Of course, the issue of physical security has not lost its fundamental relevance even now, but in the XXI century, it is significantly conditioned primarily by information security.

The term “security” has been comprehended otherwise in different periods of time in philosophy. Montesquieu, for instance, interprets security by saying that political freedom consists of security, or at least in the opinion which one has of one’s security, and Adam Smith believed that the liberty and security of an individual are the most important prerequisites for the development of public opulence; security is understood, here, as freedom from the prospect of a sudden or violent attack on one’s person or property (Rothschild, 1995, pp. 61-62). Based on the above mentioned, it can be noted that safety itself is defined by two features: physical and mental safety. At the same time, the absence of physical violence, the preservation of human rights, and freedom to act, create, and so on are important factors in the maintenance of physical and mental safety in philosophy, psychology, and other academic sciences.

“Information security” and “psychological protection”. Information is of primary importance and influence in the modern world. It can be said that “Information influence aims to systematically influence public opinion, human behavior, and decision-makers, thus affecting the functions of the society. The means of influencing through Information Operations are, for example, the distributing and highlighting of false and misleading information” (Mustonen-Ollila et al., 2020, p. 70). Meanwhile, false information can raise a number of security-related issues. Moreover, security is related to both the individual and the society and even the state. In the first and foremost sense, information security is related to cyberspace. Cyberspace is the second reality in

which various information is stored and transferred. From the point of view of philosophy, some of these theories are also based on Sun Tzu's work "The Art of War" (1988), in which the key idea is not victory with weapons, but with diplomacy and knowledge, emphasizing the information factor. It is interesting that this knowledge should not necessarily be true or verified by a moral value system, therefore the following can be stated: an important factor in maintaining information security is not only checking the reliability of the given information, but also taking into account its purpose and provision conditions, in other words, taking into account spatiotemporal, sociocultural, economic and political factors. Psychological protection is directly related to information security, as psychological protection depends on information security. In this case, psychological protection is a consequence of the development of the criteria for "filtering" information, the ability to distinguish between false and true, and a number of other factors. Psychological protection is not possible without following the rules of information security. The provided information almost always has a psychological effect: positive or negative, because essentially every piece of information contains an element of "influence". Therefore, it is believed that information security and psychological protection are connected with one another by the mechanisms of influence. If the provided information does not lead to any psychological record, then it can be said that the information has not fulfilled its task.

Philosophical and psychological mechanisms of information and psychological protection. Information security inevitably leads to psychological security. To bring forward the mechanisms of the latter, let's start with an important question: what causes information and psychological insecurity? From a philosophical point of view, the answer can be found in Kant's philosophy. Kant (1999) called for the courage to use own intelligence. When an individual is in a state of psychological and mental "infancy", he/she turns into a consumer and not a producer. Consumer psychology itself implies ready-made templates and solutions: in other words, facelessness and mass behavior, according to Musil's (1996) description: a person without qualities. Surely, with the current socio-economic and lifestyle conditions, we are dealing with deepening "infancy", and the attempts of psychological influence through information are often successful. Let's review S. Freud's theory of psychological protection. Freud was one of the first to use the term "defense mechanism" (1894). Essentially, by this Freud understood everything that Ego uses to overcome the contradictions between the unconscious and the conscious. Why? Because contradictions weaken an individual's psychological alertness and create an unstable state. And, outwardly, the less the internal conflict is, the greater is the possibility of psychological protection.

Taking into account Freud's theory, we can put forward the following formula for information protection. When a person receives certain information and has to process it according to the information he/she has, the data on this information in the conscious and unconscious may not match and create an internal conflict, and in that case it becomes easy to accept the information in the original sense and avoid the internal conflict. However, when these contradictions and inconsistencies are filtered through the method of denial and the internal conflict is overcome, we can either consider the provided information proven and accept it, or consider it unproven and reject it. Essentially Kant's formula of using their own intelligence leads to the formula of analytically accepting the received information, which becomes an important mechanism of psychological protection. Why is the mechanism of psychological protection "working" incompletely or why is it absent? The answer to this question can be found in E. Fromm's philosophical and psychological book "To Have or to Be?" (1976). When one seeks "to have" rather than "to be", production and creation cease and only consumption remains. Figuratively speaking, "to be" is a process and an endless movement, and "to have" is static and a state of immobility. Psychological protection itself is a process of creation, so whether an individual can develop a mechanism of psychological protection in the age of information technology is also a

choice between asking whether an individual prefers to have or to be, whether to consume or to create.

Conclusions. Summarizing the results of the research, the following can be noted: the relevance of this research is determined by the challenges of the modern world. It is known that the 21st century is a period of dominance of information technologies and the issues of information and psychological security are very important. Therefore, taking into account the above mentioned, the concepts of “informational intervention” and “psychological intervention” were discussed in the light of philosophy, highlighting the foundations of their origin and development in philosophy.

The origination of the terms “Information influence” and “Psychological influence” in philosophy are the result of those anthropological turns which became especially evident with the philosophy of life when ontological issues raised.

As a result of sociocultural transformations, a new type of player was formed: the “information” man. The latter chose manipulation as a tool to achieve psychological influence through information influence. Moreover, the important feature of manipulation is not the truth itself, but credibility. Particularly the mass media, which created a “distorted” image of the world, have grown into tools of “psycho-programming”.

Discussing the nature of manipulation mechanisms and information filtering tools, it becomes obvious that the concepts of “psychological protection” and “informational protection” should be based on the confirmation of *information consistency*. Due to the latter, it is possible to distinguish deception from the truth, and delusion from credibility.

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